

1 **IRX transcription factors function in transformation and metastasis.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We studied IRX transcription factor function in a variety of biologic contexts. IRX3 was repeatedly
8 modulated during melanoma progression, along with a network of genes functioning in steroid metabolism;
9 those genes included ACSL1, HSD11B2 and SRD5A1. IRX co-regulation indicated control of the androgen
10 receptor (AR) by IRX3. In addition to requirements for IRX transcription factor activity for invasive disease
11 processes like lymph node metastasis during the course of metastasis to the CNS, changes in IRX
12 expression appeared important during the course of general transformation in vitro, where it
13 transcriptionally interacted with FGFR2/3 and was associated with resistance to growth factor inhibition,
14 expression of p53 targets and an oncogenic Ras gene signature. Gene Ontology (GO) analysis indicated
15 a function for IRX transcription factors in stem cell differentiation, development and maintenance (GO BP),
16 in addition to development of multicellular organisms and organ and cell morphogenesis likely through
17 regulation of Wnt and Hippo pathways.
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